

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS IN PATIENTS AFTER CORONAVIRUS INFECTION

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The presence of an endoperiodontal focus of chronic infection in patients who have had a coronavirus infection makes it difficult to choose the tactics of managing a patient, in addition, these lesions are quite aggressive stomatogenic foci of infection that provoke focal somatic diseases [5,9,21,22]. A long-term chronic inflammatory focus in the periapical tissues is a source of autosensitization of the body [1,3,4,10-16].

Somatic pathologies (diabetes mellitus, rheumatoid arthritis, hypothyroidism, etc.) have a significant negative impact on the condition of periodontal tissues due to specific changes in metabolism and disorders of the immune system [1,2, 6-20].

The purpose of the study is to study the condition of the periodontium in patients who have had a coronavirus infection.

Materials and research methods. The material for the analysis and conclusions was the results of a survey of 30 patients with generalized periodontitis (GP) aged 30 to 55 years and disease duration from 5 to 10 years.

When compiling the groups, gender, age, concomitant somatic pathology were taken into account. Patients were randomly divided into 2 identical groups by age, 81.58% - 84.21% of patients are aged 41 years and above, while the number of patients in the groups increases with the age of the examined. In the course of the work, clinical, biochemical, radiological, statistical research methods were used.

Results and discussions. Prior to treatment, patients complained of pain when eating, talking, speech disorders, dry mouth, bleeding from the PP when brushing their teeth, and severe tooth mobility.

In addition to complaints caused by GP, this contingent of patients had complaints not typical for GP: headache, weakness, decreased ability to work, loss of sleep, appetite. A significant part (75-80%) of patients complained of paresthesia in the oral cavity and taste perversions, consisting in a decrease in taste sensitivity to sweet, salty and, to a lesser extent, sour. Obviously, these complaints are due to the presence of background pathologies.

A visual examination of the oral mucosa in patients with a coronavirus pathology of the type revealed hyperemia of the oral mucosa, its thinning, luster and, somewhat less often, turbidity.

The majority of patients (75%) complained of dry oral mucosa, in 55-60% of patients the tongue was densely coated with a grayish-white coating. An objective examination of the gums reveals a swollen, brightly colored with a cyanotic tint desquamated gingival margin, which bleeds easily on probing. Periodontal pockets with abundant purulent-bloody discharge and, often, with juicy granulations. The teeth are covered with abundant soft plaque; there are supra- and subgingival calculus. The teeth are highly mobile and easily displaced. It should be noted that the degree of tooth mobility does not correspond to the depth of the PP.

In 2 persons with intact periodontium, spontaneous bleeding of the gums, not associated with inflammation processes, was noted. In patients with generalized moderate periodontitis on the background of those who underwent coronavirus pathology, the average bleeding score was 5.66 ± 0.16 ($P < 0.01$), which corresponded to the severity of bleeding of the II-III degree (the appearance of a blood spot, as well as filling the interdental space with blood when touched with a probe).

There were no intergroup differences in the intensity of bleeding: in patients of the 1st group, it was 5.61 ± 0.25 ; in group 2 5.70 ± 0.22 points ($P > 0.05$).

At the same time, a high score of tooth mobility was established, which in generalized

moderate periodontitis patients was 4.53 ± 0.08 points, which corresponded to the displacement of the teeth in the vestibulo-oral and mediobuccal directions by more than 1 mm, as well as the displacement of the teeth in all directions.

In the tested groups of patients, no statistically significant differences in tooth mobility were found: the average score of tooth mobility in group 1 was 4.58 ± 0.15 ; in group 2 - 4.48 ± 0.12 ($P > 0.05$).

The results of the study of the depth of the PP showed that the depth of the PP, according to the applied scoring scale in the studied groups of patients, ranged from 4.77 ± 0.14 - 4.83 ± 0.11 ($P > 0.05$) points, which corresponded to the depth PP 4-6mm and more than 6mm. The mean PP depth score was 4.80 ± 0.09 .

When studying oral hygiene, it was found that OHI-S scores in both groups of patients ranged from 4.85 ± 0.09 - 4.42 ± 0.12 ($P > 0.05$). The OHI-S index score in patients with GP was 4.87 ± 0.07 . In accordance with the accepted scoring, such values of the OHI-S index corresponded to poor and very poor oral hygiene.

The study of the degree of inflammation of the gums and the severity of the destructive-inflammatory process in the periodontium according to the combined gingival-periodontal index O' Leary demonstrated the presence of an acute pronounced inflammatory process, ulceration and spontaneous bleeding from the gums, corresponding to PP- II - and III degrees.

The total severity of the inflammatory-destructive periodontal lesion according to the O' Leary index according to the point scale adopted by us was 9.21 ± 0.11 points. In the studied groups of patients, the value of the O' Leary index was determined at levels of 9.17 ± 0.21 - 9.25 ± 0.25 ($P > 0.05$).

The high scores we obtained for the clinical manifestations of generalized moderate periodontitis against the background of those who had coronavirus pathology are consistent with the literature data on the severe and aggressive course of GP in these patients.

At the same time, a detailed assessment of the clinical manifestations of GP and their evaluation in points made it possible to carry out an intergroup comparison of the studied parameters and establish the homogeneity of the clinical manifestations of GP in the compared groups.

Conclusions. The high scores we obtained for the clinical manifestations of generalized moderate periodontitis against the background of those who had coronavirus pathology are consistent with the literature data on the severe and aggressive course of generalized moderate periodontitis.

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